

DATE GPR	YEAR 2012	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: Max:	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1505 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropogenic	
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In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 2479-2483 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *two square tubo blocks*

Covered by SU: Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX				
☐ Pottery ☐ Nails ☐ Tiles ☐ Marble ☐ Amphorae ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Dolia ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tiles) ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Mortar ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☐ Glass	☐ Tufo (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% ☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive <table border="1"> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> <tr> <td> ☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft </td> <td> ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify) </td> </tr> </table>	Compaction	Color	☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft	☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: Is bound to (only for masonry):

Is abutted by: Abuts:

Is covered by: 1389 Covers:

Is cut by: Cuts:

Is filled by: Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
dry sunny conditions, SU sharp in situ, SU is visible since 2010 season

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: *south east in Area B, north east of threshold SU 1394*
 Shape: *two square blocks*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction, visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse corrugated other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Can edges: rounded straight

Cur sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:

Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):

no bc

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

two individual tufo blocks which are surrounded by soil

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

two blocks of unknown purpose sitting north east of doosteps SU 1334.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Fill ed-out by

OKM

on

25.6.2017

Revised by

OKM

on

25.6.2017

PDF'd by

low

Entered by

on